

A Study on the Academic Performance of College Teachers based on Key Performance Indicators

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the study of Academic Performance Indicators of College Teachers and their self- assessment. Academic Performance Indicator (API) is a quantitative measure that gives the growth of a student, teacher and an institution. Since 2010, API has been implemented by several universities and institutions in India. To maintain the standards of higher education, API was initiated as an attempt to link teacher's selection and their career advancement. In this paper, four categories are reviewed and these categories are compared with the other standards followed in other institutes/states.

Keywords: *Academic Performance Indicator, Career advancement, Higher education*

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is the backbone of our nation. It is an instrument to national human resource development. Listed among the fastest growing economies in the world, India stands way behind in the line, when it comes to education. Low quality education is crippling India's growth to cope with the demands of the 21st century economy [1]. To improve the students, teacher's quality should also be improved. Teaching is the primary role for all teachers. But to improve the knowledge, their academic performance also needs to be improved. Knowledge is more powerful than a sword in a war. In ancient days, "Gurukula" was the schooling methodology followed in India. The gurus (teachers) and shisyas (students) were equally benefited which imparted the tremendous knowledge to both of them. Quality is the

final result to their responsiveness and also to the need of personal development. This self development is also a benefit to staff to improve the performances in academic, teaching, career advancement/ promotions and in recruitments. In India, University Grants Commission (UGC) has introduced the Academic Performance Indicator and it is based on teaching – related activities, domain knowledge, participation in examination and evaluation, contribution to innovative teaching and new courses etc. Every year, the values are calculated. The teachers who are eligible for promotion are based on these calculated values. Many states in India performed a detailed study and guidelines to calculate API score. To maintain the quality, UGC established few regulations for the teachers in higher education regarding minimum qualifications for appointments and other academic staff in universities and colleges in 1956. These regulations were revised in 2008 and published by the Gazette of India in 2010 [2]. UGC has introduced the new academic performance indicators in 2016, which was published by Gazette of India [3]. In this paper, the key performance indicator based on UGC's Academic Performance is followed.

II. KEY ELEMENTS OF API:

Comparing to UGC's API, various colleges have framed the Key Performance Indicator for Career Advancement and Self Improvement. The Key Performance Indicator are calculated for every academic year. At the end of the academic year, the performance of the teachers are analysed based on the KPI scored values. The structure of the KPI is

presented. Staff needs to score in all the four categories. The various categories are as follows:

Category I – Continuous improvement / professional growth

The Continuous Improvement / Professional Growth is categorized in Category – I. Metrics are chosen for this criteria and the marks are allotted (Table 1). Category – I is based on the self improvement of the staff.

Table 1: Self Improvement

S. No	Metrics	Max. Score
1.	Journal Publications	20
2.	Workshops/ Seminars/ FDP/ STTP	20
3.	Conference Publications	10
4.	Sponsored projects (applied and sanctioned)	40
5.	Patent/ Copyright/ Consultancy/ Product Development	20
6.	Book/ Chapter/ Lecture Notes published	20
7.	Membership in professional bodies/ Student chapter created	20
8.	Honours /Awards/ Fellowship for Self/Department	10
9.	Research Guidance	20
10.	Maintenace of Course File	30
11.	Introducing Innovations in the Department	10
12.	Publication of articles in newspapers/ magazines; radio talks, television programmes	20
Total		240

Self improvement (continous improvement) is a process where a person tries to improve his/her knowledge. Category – I (Table 1) will help the staff to improve themselves.

Category II – Interactions with Industry

The purpose of professional education is to empower the students Industry – ready in any portfolio. Better interaction between Industry and Institution is the current need. To promote Industry – Institute interaction, category II is formed. Staff are

encouraged to interact with Institutes for Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), Centre of Excellence (CoE) and student internships & placements. The organization of workshops/ seminars and conferences in connection with Industries are focussed here. Academic Performance Indicator (API) scores for the interactions created with the students like workshops, social activities based on the teacher's self-assessment. The self-assessment score will be based on verifiable criteria and will be finalized by the Screening /Selection Committee.

Table 2: Institute – Industry interaction

S. No	Metrics	Max. Score
1.	Joint venture with Industries (MoU/CoE)	50
2.	Resource person for conferences/ workshops/ guest lecture/ seminar	20
3.	Industrial Training/ Refresher courses	10
4.	Workshop/ Seminar/ FDP organized	10
5.	Reviewers/Editor in Journals	10
6.	Societal Activities	10
Total		110

Table 2 shows the scores allotted for Institute - Industry Collaboration.

For the benefit of society, awareness's like Youth Red Cross (YRC), National Service Scheme (NSS), Blood donation camps are given in Category – II. Staff can plan their activities accordingly.

Category III - Student development

Teachers serve many other roles in the classroom. Teachers set the tone of their classrooms, build a warm environment, mentor and nurture students, become role models, and listen and look for signs of trouble. The most common role a teacher plays in the classroom is to teach knowledge to children [4]. Teachers are initially learners who help student in all academic activities. Teachers motivate students in project works, paper publication, attending symposiums and conferences [5]. Table 3 shows the scores allotted for Student interaction.

Table 3: Student Interaction

S. No	Metrics	Max. Score
1.	Mentoring (Placement, Career Growth, Disciplinary activities, Attendance)	10
2.	Internal Assessment/ End Semester Examination results	30
3.	Project Guidance	20
4.	Motivation for attending Symposiums/ Conferences/ Workshops	10
5.	Development of Audio/ Video/ Notes/ ICT	10
6.	Teaching – Learning process	20
7.	Student Feedback	10
8.	Development of Lab experiments	10
9.	Remedial/ Bridge Courses	10
Total		130

This category involves the academic scores for teaching, learning and evaluation related activities based on the self – assessment.

Category IV - Administrative commitment

Apart from teaching, staff is assigned other duties as well. Finally, Academic Performance Indicator (API) scores for the administrative commitment like placement coordinator, IQAC, NBA and NAAC coordinator, Board of Studies coordinator, Examination related work and other related activities based on the teacher's self-assessment. The self-assessment score will be based on verifiable criteria and will be finalized by the Screening /Selection Committee. The total scoring in Category – IV is 50 marks.

DISCUSSION

Keeping the UGC' s Academic Performance Indicator, the above four categories are framed. Each year, depending on the improvements in the quality of education and learning, the categories can be modified. For each academic year, the proposed scores are calculated and compared with the scores calculated at the end of the academic year. Staff are motivated to achieve the high scores.

CONCLUSION

The regulations are framed for the betterment of students, teachers as well the Institution. Teaching is mandatory requirement for all teachers. The values are calculated for each category. Based on the values scored by the staff, promotions and increments are given to the staff who obtain high marks. For low – scorers, counselling is being provided for their improvement in the next academic years.

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